

DAMAGE BEHAVIOR IN PAPER-BASED FRICTION MATERIALS SUBJECTED TO COMPRESSIVE LOADING UNDER ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

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Keywords: Paper-based friction material, Fatigue, Damage, Compression, Elevated Temperature

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with investigation on microscopic damage behavior in paper-based friction materials subjected to compressive loading at elevated temperature to clarify influence of temperature on damage. Paper-based friction materials are used for clutch discs in automatic transmissions, and they are subjected to cyclic shear-compressive loading in service. Two kinds of paper-based friction materials which were composed with aramid fiber, cellulose fiber and phenolic resin were used. The compressive fatigue tests were conducted at room temperature (R.T.) and 120°C in air. After the tests, damage initiated during the fatigue tests was observed. Damage density in both materials increased with increasing load cycles for all conditions, and damage density also increased with increasing temperature. The paper-based friction materials were susceptible to damage at elevated temperature. From the viewpoint the constituents, damage density in the cellulose-based material was much higher than in the aramid-based material.

1 INTRODUCTION

Friction materials are used for clutch discs and brake discs in vehicles because of their high friction performance. A clutch and brake are mechanical devices which accelerate, slow or stop an automobile to control its transport speed by friction transmission, and the motional property and reliability depend on their mechanical properties. Paper-based friction materials which are composites consisting of organic synthetic fibers and high-temperature resin are used for clutch discs. It is demanded that paper-based friction materials have a variety of superior characteristics. For example, high friction properties are desired to improve power transmission, and wear resistance, heat resistance and strength are also needed to guarantee their reliability in practical use.

To manufacture paper-based friction materials with high performances, many studies have been conducted. Friction properties [1, 2], relationship between constitutions and friction properties [3], contact properties between friction materials and other materials [4-7], and dynamic compressive behavior [8-11] were investigated. To guarantee their long-term durability, a little studies on their strength [12] and fatigue property [13-17] have been reported. The authors conducted out-of-plane cyclic compressive tests of paper-based friction materials which were composed with aramid fiber, cellulose fiber and phenolic resin at room temperature in air to investigate their fatigue strength and fatigue mechanism [18]. During the tests, evolution of microscopic damage was observed to evaluate influence of applied stress and load cycle on damage initiation. As a result, damage in the paper-based friction materials initiated and accumulated under cyclic compressive loading, and damage density increased with increasing compressive stress and load cycle. The failure mechanism in compressive fatigue was explained by damage initiation under high compressive stress. Although these experiments

were conducted at room temperature, paper-based friction materials are generally used at elevated temperature in oil, and influence of environmental condition on damage remains to be clarified.

In this study, fatigue tests of the paper-based friction materials for clutch discs under out-of-plane compressive loading at elevated temperature in air were conducted to investigate damage behaviour at elevated temperature. Incremental compressive cyclic loading tests were also conducted to investigate influence of compressive stress and temperature on damage.

2 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN

Aramid-based material and cellulose-based friction material were used. The aramid-based material and cellulose-based material are composed of aramid fiber of 70 wt% and phenolic resin of 30 wt%, and cellulose fiber of 70 wt% and phenolic resin of 30 wt%, respectively. Porosity of the aramid-based material and cellulose-based material is 55.8 % and 56.6 % measured by the mercury intrusion method, respectively. Figures 1 and 2 show microstructures of the aramid-based material and cellulose-based material, respectively. The direction of fibers is random in the in-plane direction, and the fibers are stacked like layers in the thickness direction in both materials.

To create specimens for compressive tests, the materials with thickness of 1.1 mm were cut into square shape with 10 mm on a side. Preliminarily, flat section on side of the specimen was created by a cross-section polishing apparatus (CP) to observe the section by a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

To conduct out-of-plane compressive tests at elevated temperature, a new jig was made. Figure 3 shows photograph of the jig and detail of a specimen stage. The jig have heat sinks and cooling fans

Figure 1: Microstructure of the aramid-based material

Figure 2: Microstructure of the cellulose-based material

to prevent a testing apparatus from elevating temperature, and a specimen stage have a band heater and thermostat to control temperature of the stage. Temperature of the stage could be controlled to be up to 200 °C using this jig.

Incremental compressive cyclic loading tests were carried out to examine influence of compressive stress on damage. An experimental procedure is shown in Fig. 4. At first, the specimen was put on the lower stage. Then, the upper jig was dropped, and the specimen was placed in contact with the lower and upper stages. After that, the lower and upper stages were heated. After temperature of the jigs became given temperature, out-of-plane compressive stress was applied. The compressive loading at room temperature (R.T.) and 120°C was repeated five cycles, and then, the maximum stress was increased stepwise up to 100 MPa. Note that temperature of paper-based friction materials in actual use is about 120°C. After the fifth cycle at stress level of 5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 MPa, the section made by a CP was observed with a SEM.

Compressive fatigue tests were conducted to examine influence of load cycles on damage behavior. The experimental procedure is shown in Fig. 5. The compressive fatigue tests were carried out under sinusoidal cyclic load with the frequency of 1 Hz (up to 10² cycles) or 10 Hz (more than 10² cycles), the compressive stress was ranged from 1 MPa to 10 MPa at R.T. and 120°C. After 10¹, 10², 10³, 10⁴ and 10⁵ cycles, the section made by a CP was observed with a SEM.

(a) Overall view (b) Lower jig
Figure 3: New jig for compressive tests at elevated temperature

Figure 4: Loading schedule of incremental compressive cyclic loading tests.

Figure 5: Loading schedule of compressive fatigue tests.

2.3 DAMAGE OBSERVATION

Damage detected in the observation sites was categorized as interfacial debonding between fiber and resin, damage in fiber, damage in resin, and unidentified damage. Length of all damage sites was measured, and damage density D_L is defined by a ratio of total length of damage to total observation area as in eq. (1).

$$D_L = \sum_i a_i / \sum_j S_j \quad (1)$$

where a_i is the length of each damage and S_j is the area of each observation site. The length of damage a_i is defined by distance in a straight line between both edges of damage. The damage density was measured for each damage type as follows;

$$D_L^{Total} = D_L^{Debonding} + D_L^{Fiber} + D_L^{Resin} + D_L^{Unidentified} \quad (2)$$

where the superscripts of D_L denote the damage types. This damage evaluation technique in this study was similar to the previous study [18].

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 INFLUENCE OF COMPRESSIVE STRESS ON DEFORMATION AND DAMAGE

The hysteresis loops of aramid-based material and cellulose-based material of the fifth cycle for each stress level at R.T. and 120 °C are shown in Fig. 6. In both materials, the hysteresis loop shifted to the high strain direction and its gradient became steep with increasing stress level. To evaluate mechanical properties of each material under compressive loading, the maximum strain ε_0 , strain range $\Delta\varepsilon$ and unloading elastic modulus E at each stress level were examined. The unloading elastic modulus was defined as a slope of the unloading relation from the maximum stress of hysteresis loop.

Figure 7 shows the maximum strain, strain range, unloading elastic modulus as functions of the maximum compressive stress in both materials. In both materials, the maximum strain and unloading elastic modulus increased with increasing maximum compressive stress, while the strain range remained as constant low value. For the aramid-based materials, the maximum strain at 120 °C were lower than that at R.T, while the unloading elastic modulus at 120 °C were higher than that at R.T. On the other hand, for the cellulose-based materials, the maximum strain and unloading elastic modulus at 120 °C were higher than those at R.T. These results are explained as follows; the paper-based friction materials are porous materials with porosity of about 60%, and their porosity decreases with increasing

(a) Aramid-based material

(b) Cellulose-based material

Figure 6: Hysteresis loops for each stress level at R.T. and 120 °C

compressive stress, and then the paper-based friction materials become dense. Hence, the unloading elastic modulus becomes high with increasing compressive stress. From a viewpoint of influence of temperature, deformability of phenolic resin at elevated temperature is higher than that at R.T., and damage easily occurs at elevated temperature, as mentioned in Sec. 3.2. Therefore, the maximum strains of both materials become high. Change of the unloading elastic modulus at elevated temperature depends on constituents of the materials due to their temperature-dependent densification behavior.

3.2 INFLUENCE OF COMPRESSIVE STRESS ON DAMAGE

Figure 8 shows typical damage of the aramid-based and cellulose-based materials subjected to compressive stress of 50 MPa at 120 °C, respectively. The interfacial debonding between thin and thick fibers are observed in the aramid-based material. In the cellulose-based material, interfacial debonding and damage in fiber are observed.

Figure 9 shows damage density of the aramid-based material at R.T. and 120 °C as a function of compressive stress. In this figure, the damage density of each damage type and summation of all damage densities are plotted. The damage density at R.T. and 120 °C increased with increasing compressive stress, and damage in fiber was the most common damage type. The damage densities of all damage types increased with elevating temperature.

Figure 7: Maximum strain, strain range, unloading elastic modulus as functions of the maximum compressive stress

Figure 8: Damage behavior (50MPa, 120 °C)

Figure 9: Damage density in aramid-based material as a function of compressive stress.

Figure 10: Damage density in cellulose-based material as a function of compressive stress.

Figure 10 shows damage density of the cellulose-based material at R.T. and 120 °C as a function of compressive stress. The damage density at R.T. and 120 °C also increased with increasing compressive stress, and interfacial debonding was the most common damage type. The damage densities of all damage types increased with elevating temperature. Compared with damage behavior in the aramid-based material, the damage density of the cellulose based material is much higher than that of the aramid-based material.

3.3 INFLUENCE OF LOAD CYCLES ON DAMAGE

Figure 11 shows typical damage of the aramid-based and cellulose-based materials during fatigue tests at 120 °C. The interfacial debonding between thick fibers and damage in fiber are observed in the aramid-based material. In the cellulose-based material, interfacial debonding, damage in fiber are observed.

(a) Aramid-based material (10⁶ cycles)

(b) Cellulose-based material (10⁵ cycles)

Figure 11: Damage behavior during fatigue tests (120 °C)

(a) R.T. [18]

(b) 120 °C

Figure 12: Damage density in the aramid-based material as a function of load cycles.

(a) R.T. [18]

(b) 120 °C

Figure 13: Damage density in the cellulose-based material as a function of load cycles.

Figure 12 shows damage density of the aramid-based material at R.T. and 120 °C as a function of load cycles. The damage density increased with increasing compressive stress, and damage in fiber was the most common damage type, irrespective of temperature. The damage densities of all damage types increased with elevating temperature.

Figure 13 shows damage density of the cellulose-based material at R.T. and 120 °C as a function of

load cycles. The damage density also increased with increasing compressive stress, and interfacial debonding was the most common damage type, irrespective of temperature. The damage densities of all damage types also increased with elevating temperature. The damage density of the cellulose based material is much higher than that of the aramid-based material.

From the results of Incremental compressive cyclic loading tests and fatigue tests, the paper-based friction materials are more susceptible to damage at elevated temperature than at R.T. Moreover, the aramid-based material is more resistible to damage than the cellulose-based material.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, incremental compressive cyclic loading tests and fatigue tests of paper-based friction materials for clutch discs were conducted at room temperature and elevated temperature in air to investigate influence of load cycle and compressive stress on damage. The conclusions obtained in this investigation are as follows:

1. The damage in the aramid-based material and cellulose-based material initiated and accumulated under cyclic compressive loading, and the damage density increased with increasing compressive stress and load cycles.
2. The damage density increased with elevating temperature, and the paper-based materials are susceptible to damage at elevated temperature.
3. The aramid-based material had higher resistance to the damage initiation under compressive stress than the cellulose-based material.

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